

Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS

Development of a national energy system model – Project Overview

Please use the following citation for:

- **This Activity**

Plazas-Niño, F. (2024, April). Energy System Modelling Using OSeMOSYS: Development of a national energy system model – Project Overview (Version 1.0).

- **OSeMOSYS UI Software**

Climate Compatible Growth. (2024). MUIO (Version v5.0.0). GitHub. <https://github.com/ClimateCompatibleGrowth/MUIO>

- **OSeMOSYS Google Forum**

If you are stuck, please ask questions [here](#). If you get ahead, please answer questions in the same forum. Please state that you are using the 'OSeMOSYS UI' and not 'ClicSAND'.

Objective

The purpose of this project is to apply the concepts learned about long-term energy system analysis to evaluate energy planning in a country. By creating a fully functioning OSeMOSYS model, the project aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of how to perform national energy system modelling using a free and open-source energy planning model. This model can then be utilized by other stakeholders for analysis purposes. The technical and socio-economic analyses conducted as part of this project aim to identify areas of key research needed in your national context. Additionally, the project intends to serve as a baseline for strengthening research skills and promoting the development of research outcomes, such as peer-reviewed articles and conference presentations.

Activities

First task:

1. Create an OSeMOSYS model for your country from scratch with the latest available data. This will include:

- a. Gathering and calibrating technology data, encompassing Capital costs, variable costs, fixed costs, capacity factors, input and output activity ratios.
- b. Gathering and calibrating existing installed capacity data, including Residual capacity, capacity factors, fixed costs, variable costs, efficiencies.
- c. Gathering and calibrating demand data, including Demand for electricity defined by sectors, if possible, demand for transport defined by type.

Second Task:

1. Creating at least three long term energy scenarios:

- a. The scenarios are to be based on relevant literature review, with justification being provided as to why those three scenarios specifically were created.
- b. One of the scenarios must serve as a 'base' scenario, with a least cost scenario acting as this, unless another scenario is chosen with justified reasons. The scenarios must be pragmatic, meaning that capital cost investment needs to be evenly distributed, and the time frame of the scenarios must be at least up to 2040.

Third Task:

1. Writing an academic paper, utilizing the model from the First Task and the scenarios from the Second Task, with the provision of technical and socio-economic analysis. The paper must include the below structure:

- a. An abstract.
- b. An introduction: i. General introduction, covering the need for decarbonization. ii. Introduction of the country context in terms of decarbonization. iii. A short literature review, with a description of existing models (if there are any).
- c. Methodology: i. Description of OSeMOSYS as modelling framework and why OSeMOSYS is being used as the tool for analysis. ii- Description of the Reference Energy System (RES). iii- Description of the data gathering and calibrating, and model creation. It implies a detailed explanation of how the OSeMOSYS model is created, listing of all the data sources and data manipulations conducted in order to obtain a fully functioning model. iv- Scenario

identification and explanation: In detail justification of chosen scenarios, with explanation of how the scenarios are created (e.g., what constraints are applied to the model to create the scenarios).

d. Results: Presenting of results per scenario, or combined, including: 1. Annual electricity production. 2. Annual installed capacity. 3. Transport sector. 4. CO2 emission timeline. 5. Total system costs.

e. Discussion: i. Findings and policy insights - this section analyzes simulated scenarios, highlighting trends and offering valuable policy recommendations. ii- Limitations and opportunities of further research: Authors depict the constraints of the current energy modelling approach while highlighting potential directions for future research.

f. Conclusion: Concluding remarks regarding work conducted.

2. Preparing a 15–20-minute presentation to showcase the analysis conducted in the paper